

COARSE AND FINE SEDIMENT AUGMENTATIONS IN RIVERS

BSC THESIS

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The cover photo is an aerial photo of the shoal front during the coarse shoal experiment.

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by

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PREFACE

This Bachelor Thesis is the last fulfilment in order to finish the Bachelor programme in Civil Engineering at Delft University of Technology. To complete this thesis 8 weeks have been spend on research and flume experiments.

Flume experiments were done to gain more insight in the propagation and behaviour of coarse and fine sediment augmentations in rivers. The experiments done were also part of the Sorting Workshop that was held in Delft in May 2015. Doing the experiments at the workshop gave me the opportunity to get feedback, advise and thoughts on the provisional results from experts in the field of river morphodynamics. Some of the feedback was going beyond the scope of this thesis, but it was a great learning experience and it made me even more curious.

My special thanks go to my supervisors. First to Astrid Blom, for the help and feedback while writing and the opportunity for doing flume experiments for my bachelor thesis. Secondly to Victor Chavarrias because of all the help with doing the experiments and the Matlab problems.

Lieke Lokin

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ABSTRACT

In river restoration projects sediment augmentations are already an established method for either compensation for erosion or improving the grain size distribution in the bed surface. However little is known about the effect of the grain sizes in augmentations on the downstream bed. In this thesis an experimental study is done on the effect of a fine and a coarse sediment augmentation on a mixed bed with two different fractions of fine gravel. Three flume experiments were done, first one was to find the normal conditions for which a mixed bed is mobile. In the second two experiments a shoal of first fine and secondly coarse sediment was installed and the behaviour of the shoal was measured while it propagated over the mixed bed. The main conclusions were that in the fine shoal experiment the downstream reach was almost not affected by the presence of the shoal, while in the coarse shoal experiment there was significant erosion of the downstream bed.

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NOMENCLATURE

B	Width of the flume	[m]
c_f	Dimensionless friction coefficient	[-]
D	Mean grain size	[m]
D_{50}	Mean grain size	[m]
F_{Ai}	Areal fraction content of size fraction i	[-]
F_{Ak}	Areal fraction content of size fraction k	[-]
F_{Vi}	Volume fraction content of size fraction i	[-]
Fr	Froude number	[-]
g	Gravitational acceleration	[m/s ²]
h	Water depth	[m]
h_n	Normal water depth	[m]
i_b	Bed slope	[-]
q	Specific discharge	[m ² /s]
Q	Discharge	[m ³ /s]
Re	Reynolds number	[-]
s	Sediment discharge per unit width (specific sediment discharge)	[m ² /s]
S	Sediment discharge	[m ³ /s]
t	Time	[s]
u	Flow velocity	[m/s]
V_s	Volume of sediment discharged	[m ³]
Δ	Relative sediment density $\Delta = \rho_s/\rho - 1$	[-]
Δm	Increase in mass	[kg]
θ	Shields parameter	[-]
ν	Kinematic viscosity $\nu = 1.307 * 10^{-6}$	[m ² /s]
ρ	Water density $\rho = 1000$	[kg/m ³]
ρ_s	Density of $\rho_s = 2650$	[kg/m ³]

1. INTRODUCTION

Engineered measures to make rivers more suitable for shipping, to create water supply or to improve flood safety have caused river bed degradation. The construction of groynes and dikes in the last decades/centuries have shifted the equilibrium state of rivers to a state with a reduced channel slope which causes degradation. Dams for hydropower or water supply block the upstream sediment load, downstream of the dams a sediment deficit is created, which will cause increased erosion to compensate the deficit. The degradation of the riverbed disrupts the ecosystem, can undermine structures, can lead to more intrusion of salt seawater to upstream areas and can cause navigational bottlenecks. Riverbeds can be protected from further degradation by sediment augmentation in upstream regions. This is already an established method, but still there is little known about the physical behaviour of these augmentations and their effect on the initial bed.

A sediment augmentation is the opposite of dredging, where sediment is taken out of a river. After such measures in rivers, the river will respond to the new situation in a way that a new equilibrium state will be established. In the equilibrium state there is no net change in the river. This does not mean that there is no sediment transport in the equilibrium state, this means that there is no net erosion or aggradation. The sediment discharge entering an river reach will also leave that reach. If sediment with a different grain size is added to a river this will also have an effect on the equilibrium state. The mobility of a grain depends on three main forces, gravity, the shear force due to the flow and the normal forces of the interaction with the other grains. The resulting force in the direction of the flow determines whether or not a grain is mobile (*de Vriend et al. 2011*). In general fine grains are more mobile than coarser ones. In mixed beds, where a fine and a coarse fraction are present, coarser fractions are more mobile than in uniform beds while for the finer fractions are less mobile. This effect is called hiding, the smaller grains get shelter from the coarser ones, being less exposed to the flow. While the coarser grains are more exposed and so a larger shear force is acting on them, making them more mobile (*Southard, 2006*).

Ecosystems can be restored with augmentations. Salmon and trout need certain grainsizes for their spawning, these fish spawn near the place where they were born. These fish need specific grain sizes to make their redd, nest, this is mostly coarse gravel. If the bed material is too coarse the fish are not able to move the grains and thus cannot make a redd, but if the bed material is too fine the redd will erode or fine sand will fill the pores between the coarse grains (*Riebe et al. 2014*). Fine gravels and coarse sand with grain sizes between 0.5 and 4 mm are also needed, they filter out the finer sediments and so protect the redd from clogging by the finer sediments and the water flow, and thus the incoming flux of oxygen from being blocked (*Franssen et al. 2014*). Downstream of dams a lack of coarser sediment is created because most often the bed load is blocked by the dam. To predict whether or not a restoration project with sediment augmentations will have the intended effect, the knowledge of the influence of the augmentation on the bed and the propagation celerity is essential.

The sediment from the augmentations will be transported downstream. As fine grains are entrained more easily and thus transported by the flow more easily than the coarser grains, the fine grains will travel faster than the coarser grains.

Flume experiments done by Sklar et al. (2009) and Venditti et al. (2010) studied the influence of augmentations on riverbeds that are cut off from the upstream sediment supply by a dam. Here sediment pulses were added to relatively unimodal beds. After a simulation of a dam closure by stopping the initial sediment feed, the bed became armoured and immobile. In order to study the influence of sediment augmentations on the grain size distribution of the bed, fine and coarse pulses with different grain sizes, fine and coarser but both smaller than the median bed grain size, were added. The finer augmentations caused a great decrease of the median bed grain size, however the duration of this change was of limited time. The fine pulses travelled with a high

celerity. The coarser augmentations had less impact on the median grain size but still it decreased and caused a slight improvement, there were more smaller grains present in the bed. The improvement was less with the coarser augmentation, but the over-all effect was bigger while the duration of the improvement was longer (*Sklar et al. 2009*). The effect of the armouring was decreased and after the pulses passed, a more bimodal bed was created (*Venditti et al. 2010*).

The bed disturbances and the change in the grain size distribution travel downstream and can both be described as a wave with a celerity. Numerical models have shown that the wave of grain size distribution precedes the change in bed level and even diminishes the change in bed slope (*Mosselman and Sloff, 2007*) (*Ribberink, 1987*). *Berkhout (2015)* found in experiments with a bimodal bed, sand and fine gravel, that an aggradational coarsening wave is preceded by a degradation wave. This effect may be of greater importance.

In his master thesis *Berkhout (2015)* did flume experiments with sand and fine gravel. First an experiment with a uniform bed, made out of the fine gravel, and the same size sediment shoal was done. First the front of shoal started to steepen while sediment from upstream travelled over the shoal, but within an hour the shoal started to propagate and flatten out in time. In the second experiment the bed was replaced by a mixture of sand and fine gravel. The mixture showed to be fine enough to develop dunes downstream. Directly downstream the shoal front a scour was formed, this resulted in a fining degradation wave in front of the propagation shoal. While dunes were formed in the finer sediment, it is expected that with a coarser bed this effect will not occur.

This study will look into the effects of both a coarse and fine augmentation on a mixed fine gravel bed. Instead of sediment pulses a shoal, long enough for not having to feed, will be installed upstream. The mixed bed will be coarse enough so that bed forms are not likely to be formed.

2. OBJECTIVE

The aim of this Bachelor Thesis is to study the propagation of a shoal composed of either fine or coarse sediment on a mixed-size sediment bed. In laboratory experiments in a controlled setting, it is possible to measure changes in bed elevation, grain size distribution and sediment discharge. This can be analysed to gain more insight in the behaviour of augmentations of different sediment sizes on mixed sediment beds.

2.1 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions will be answered during in this Bachelor Thesis to achieve the objective.

1. What are the normal conditions for a mixed-sized gravel bed under uniform flow in a controlled environment (flume experiment)?
2. What is the influence of a shoal composed of respectively fine and coarse sediment fraction on the initial bed?
3. What is the difference in propagation celerity and behaviour of a shoal of respectively fine and coarse sediment?

2.2 METHODOLOGY

In order to answer the research questions a set of three experiments are done.

1. An experiment with only a mixed bed with a constant elevation is done to determine the normal conditions. These conditions are used in the following experiments. In the second experiment a fine shoal will be installed upstream. The sediment in the mixed bed contained two sediment fractions that are both coloured in a different colour.
2. An experiment with a fine shoal. In the upstream reach of the bed a fine shoal is installed while the downstream reach consists of only the mixed sediment. The sediment in the shoal has its natural colour. The colour difference between the shoal and the downstream reach makes it possible to track the sediment material.
3. A third experiment is done similar to the fine shoal experiment where the fine sediment in the shoal is replaced with coarse sediment.

Further description of the experimental setup and the experiments will be given in Chapter 3.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP AND MEASUREMENTS

3.1 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The experiments are done in a tilting flume in the Water Laboratory of the Faculty of Civil Engineering and Geosciences at Delft University of Technology. All experiments are done with a mixed-size (bimodal) sediment bed with a fine fraction with a grain size of 2.2 mm and a coarse fraction of 4.4 mm. Both fractions are coloured in different colours. In the second and third experiment a shoal will be installed in the upstream reach. In all the experiments there will be no sediment feed. The bed elevation during the experiment will be measured using laser instruments, the areal fraction content of the different size fractions at the bed surface will be measured using the image analysis described by Orrú et al. (2014). Below the three experiments are shortly described:

- E1. An experiment with a constant bimodal bed, with normal flow in the flume. This experiment is done to establish the normal flow conditions and to estimate the friction and the sediment transport rate under the normal flow conditions. The coarse and fine fraction are in weight equally present in the bed. The bed is installed over the whole experimental domain of the flume. By adjusting the discharge, slope and downstream water level the most suitable normal flow conditions can be found.
- E2. At the upstream end of the flume a shoal made out of the fine fraction is installed. This fraction has the natural colour of the sediment, the colour difference between the fractions makes it possible track the propagation of the shoal through the domain of the flume. The shoal is 2 cm thicker than the bed and is 4 m long. The full depth of the shoal will consist of shoal material.

FIGURE 1 SCHEMATIC OF THE SECOND EXPERIMENT: SHOAL MADE OUT OF THE FINE FRACTION

- E3. The same will be done as in experiment 2, but with the a shoal made out of the coarse sediment fraction of the bed. The coarse sediment in the shoal has the natural colour.

FIGURE 2 SCHEMATIC OF THE THIRD EXPERIMENT: SHOAL MADE OUT OF THE COARSE FRACTION

3.2 FLUME

The flume used has a total length of 14 meters, but the effective length for the experiment and measurements is about 10 meters. The cross section of the flume is constant over the total

length. At the upstream end a flow diverter is installed to reduce the turbulence of the incoming flow. Right upstream of the bed a wooden structure is built to gradually lead the flow over the bed, the structure leads the flow onto the bed without disrupting the upstream end of the bed.

TABLE 1 MEASUREMENTS OF THE FLUME

Length	14.0	[m]
Length for experiment	12	[m]
Width	0.4	[m]
Height	0.45	[m]
Slope (max.)	0.04	[–]
Discharge (max.)	0.088	[m ³ s ⁻¹]

In the experiment the slope and discharge are determined by the capability of the flow to be able to entrain both fractions in the sediment as a lower bound and as an upper bound the requirement of subcritical flow over the whole domain of the experiment. The upper bound of these values is determined by the flume specifications. Experiment 1 (E1) is used to determine the slope, discharge and downstream water depth under normal flow conditions that will be imposed in Experiment 2 (E2) and 3 (E3) with the shoal.

3.3 BED PROPERTIES

In the initial bed, the entire bed in E1 and the bed downstream the shoal in E2 and E3, the coarse and fine fractions are equally present. 50% of the bed sediment is the coarse fraction and the other 50% the fine fraction.

The thickness of the bed is 18 cm over the whole domain of the Experiment E1, the length of the bed for E1 is approximately 10 m. For E2 and E3 the bed thickness is determined by the wooden structure that is installed upstream in the flume to lead the flow onto the bed without substantial disturbances. The shoal is 4 m long and is 2 cm thicker than the mixed bed. This means that the difference in elevation between the downstream reach and the shoal reach is 2 cm. Table 2 lists the bed properties.

TABLE 2 BED PROPERTIES

	E1	E2	E3
Bed thickness [m]	0.12	0.18	
Shoal length [m]	0	4	
Shoal thickness [m]	0	0.02	
Coarse fraction in the bed	0.5	0.5	0.5
Fine fraction in the bed	0.5	0.5	0.5
Coarse fraction in the shoal	0	0	1
Fine fraction in the shoal	0	1	0

3.4 SEDIMENT

The two sediment fractions used are fine gravels. The fine fraction consists of grain sizes between 1.7 and 2.5 mm with a D_{50} of 2.2 mm, the coarse fraction has grain sizes between 3 and 5 mm with a D_{50} of 4.4 mm. In the bed material the fine fraction is coloured blue and the coarse fraction pink. In Experiment 2 and 3 the sediment in the shoal has its natural colour. The density of both fractions is 2650 kg/m³.

3.5 MEASUREMENTS

During the experiments specific measurements are done in three categories; the bed, the flow and the bed load. The different aspects that are measured, are listed below.

- Bed level over the whole domain

- Grain size distribution at the bed surface
- Water level
- Water discharge
- Sediment discharge downstream

The bed and water level and the grain size distribution need to be measured as often as possible at the beginning of the experiments, because most changes will occur in the first 1 to 2 hours of the experiments. This will be at a frequency of measuring once per 10 to 15 minutes. After this time the measuring frequency can be lowered to once per 30 minutes. The water discharge and the sediment discharge measure automatically and continuously.

In the next paragraphs the different measuring methods are further explained.

3.5.1 BED LEVEL AND WATER LEVEL

The bed elevation and water level are measured with laser instruments. One laser reflects on the bed and the other on the water surface. With the return time of the laser the both elevations can be calculated. The lasers are attached to a cart that rolls over the rails on the flume, a photo of the cart can be found in Appendix A

3.5.2 GRAIN SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF THE BED SURFACE

Using image analysis the grain size distribution of the top layer of the bed can be measured. The sediment in the shoal and both the fractions in the bed have distinct colours to be able to distinguish them. The pictures are taken with a camera through a glass boat that is placed on the flowing water Appendix A. The boat flattens the bed for taking the pictures, so disturbances in the water surface will not refract the light and disturb the picture.

Using image analysis in Matlab the percentage of pixels of each sediment fraction can be calculated. The percentage of pixels per fraction is equal to the surface area percentage. With the surface area percentages, F_{Ai} , the volumetric percentage of each fraction, F_{Vi} , can be calculated with the following formula (Orrú et al. 2014):

$$F_{Vi} = \frac{F_{Ai}\sqrt{D_i}}{\sum_{k=1}^N(F_{Ak}\sqrt{D_k})} \quad [1]$$

Where F_{Vi} is the volumetric percentage of fraction i , F_{Ai} is the aerial percentage of fraction i , D_i is the mean grainsize of fraction i [m], N is the number of fractions and i and k are the fractions.

3.5.3 WATER DISCHARGE

At the upstream end of the flume a discharge meter is installed. This measures the discharge all the time. The discharge can also be measured with the Rehbock weir that is installed in the return flow. From the water depth above the weir and the width of the return flow the discharge can be calculated. Both can be used to measure the discharge in a situation when no water is extracted from the flow, but while the sediment pump (see 3.5.4) is turned on it not only pumps sediment but also water from the sediment trap and so the Rehbock does not give the right value. Also the weir needs some time to adjust to a change in discharge, but the value given is more stable. The discharge meter can be connected to a computer to continuously measure the discharge. The discharge meter gives an instantaneous value and reacts directly to changes in discharge. Because of the instantaneous value and the use of the sediment pump the discharge meter is used. Appendix A shows the flow meter.

3.5.4 SEDIMENT DISCHARGE

The downstream sediment discharge is measured with a plastic box filled with water and placed on a scale. A sediment trap is placed at the downstream end of the flume. A pump in the sediment trap pumps the grains to the plastic box, because the box is entirely filled with water the water will flow out of the box while the sediment is flowing in. With the difference in weight over time the mass and the volume of the sediment flowing into the box can be calculated. With

the time differences between measurements and the density of the sediment the downstream sediment discharge and flow can be calculated. Below are the formulas for the volume of the sediment in the box and for the sediment load. Appendix A shows the sediment trap at the downstream end of the flume and the box respectively. With the following formulas the sediment discharge can be calculated.

$$V_s = \frac{\Delta m}{\rho_s - \rho} \quad [2]$$

$$S = V_s/t \quad [3]$$

$$s = S/B \quad [4]$$

Where V_s is the volume of sediment that entered the sediment trap in m^3 , Δm is the increase in mass of the box [kg], ρ_s is the density of the sediment [$2650 \text{ kg}/m^3$], ρ is the density of water [$1000 \text{ kg}/m^3$], S is the sediment discharge in [m^3/s], t is the time interval in s , s is the sediment discharge per unit width [m^2/s] and B is the width of the flume [0.40 m].

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 NORMAL FLOW (E1)

This experiment is done to determine the normal flow conditions. This is done by imposing a discharge, water depth and the bed slope on the bed for which the water depth is constant over the whole reach, the slope in water and bed level is equal (Figure 3). Both the fractions must be mobile when this flow is imposed on the bed, also the Froude number must not be too high to guarantee that the flow condition will stay subcritical when the flow is imposed on Experiment 2 and 3. By increasing or decreasing the discharge, slope and downstream water level the optimal normal flow condition was found.

FIGURE 3 WATER LEVEL AND BED LEVEL IN THE NORMAL FLOW CONDITION IN E1. THE WATER AND BED LEVEL HAVE EQUAL SLOPES. THE RAILS ON THE FLUME HAVE THE SAME SLOPE AS THE FLUME, SO THE FRAME OF REFERENCE FOR IS PARALLEL TO THE FLUME AND NOT TO THE GROUND. THE SLOPE WAS MEASURED AFTERWARDS.

4.1.1 FLOW CONDITIONS

The water depth is calculated applying a linear fit to the measured data. Figure 4 shows the linear fit to the measured data. the water depth shows a small M2 curve of -0.0001 , which is small compared to the water depth of 15.5 cm (Figure 4).

With the geometry of the flume, water depth, discharge and the slope the other flow parameters, the flow velocity, the Froude number and the friction coefficient, can be calculated with the following formulas.

FIGURE 4 WATER DEPTH FOR THE NORMAL FLOW CONDITION

The flow velocity.

$$u = \frac{Q}{Bh} \quad [5]$$

Where u is the flow velocity [m/s], Q is the water discharge [m^3/s], B is the width [m] and h is the water depth [m].

With the equilibrium water depth, which is the water depth under the normal condition, the friction coefficient can be calculated.

$$c_f = \frac{h_n^3 g i_b}{q^2} \quad [6]$$

Where c_f is the dimensionless friction coefficient [-], h_n is the equilibrium depth [m], g is the gravitational acceleration [m/s^2], i_b is the bed slope [-] and q is the specific discharge ($q = Q/B$) [m^2/s].

Froude number

$$Fr = \frac{u}{\sqrt{gh_n}} \quad [7]$$

Where Fr is the Froude number [-].

TABLE 3 FLOW PARAMETERS E1

Variable		Value	
Flow velocity	u	0.645	m/s
Froude	Fr	0.523	-
Friction coefficient	c_f	0.0066	-

The Froude number is around 0.5 which is subcritical and it is not expected that the value above the shoals will exceed 1. Because the height of the shoal will be small relative to the water depth. The water depth was stable, hence, was the Froude number over the whole bed.

4.1.2 SEDIMENT TRANSPORT

During the experiment both the different fractions were moving. Using the Shields number and diagram this can be checked with existing theory. To use the Shields diagram the Reynolds number and the Shields number are calculated with the following formulas.

$$\theta = \frac{c_f u^2}{\Delta g D} \quad [8]$$

$$Re = \frac{\sqrt{c_f} u D}{\nu} \quad [9]$$

Where θ is the Shields number [-], Δ is the relative sediment density [-], Re is the Reynolds number [-] and ν is the kinematic viscosity [m^2/s].

TABLE 4 SHIELDS AND REYNOLDS NUMBERS FOR THE DIFFERENT GRAIN SIZES

D [m]	0.0044	0.0022
θ [-]	0.0384	0.0769
Re [-]	176.1	88.06

FIGURE 5 SHIELDS DIAGRAM (DE VRIEND ET AL. 2011). PINK IS THE COARSE SEDIMENT AND BLUE THE FINE.

The Shields diagram shows that the fine fraction was theoretically mobile but the coarse fraction not. However the Shields diagram accounts for uniform sediment and not for mixed beds. In a mixed bed the mobility of fine grains is less than in uniform beds and the mobility of coarse grains is higher. This is because of the hiding effects in mixed beds. The smaller particles can hide behind and get shelter from the flow by the bigger particles and the bigger particles are more exposed to the flow. When a particle is more exposed to the flow the forces acting on it due to the flow are larger and the particle will be mobile with a lower flow.

The downstream sediment discharge was not measured during this experiment.

The presence of the fractions in the bed is shown in Figure 6. Another figure that shows both the areal and volumetric fractions can be found in Appendix B. The initial bed has some peaks in the distribution for both fractions, but after the flow started the sharp peaks are flattened out. These peaks are created while flattening the bed, the flattening caused an overrepresentation of the coarse fraction. On average the bed kept an equal distribution between the two fractions. The graph shows there is not a consistent trend in fining or coarsening in the bed.

TABLE 5 REACH AVERAGES OF THE VOLUMETRIC DISTRIBUTION OF THE COARSE AND FINE FRACTIONS IN THE BED, FOR THE INITIAL SITUATION BEFORE THE FLOW STARTED, DIRECTLY AFTER THE FLOW WAS STARTED AND AFTER THE EXPERIMENT FINISHED.

	Volumetric fractions average	
	Coarse	Fine
Initial	0.5434	0.4566
Start flow	0.5074	0.4926
Final	0.5081	0.4919

FIGURE 6 VOLUMETRIC DISTRIBUTION OF THE COARSE FRACTION OF THE INITIAL BED, RIGHT AFTER THE EXPERIMENT STARTED AND THE FINAL BED

4.2 FINE SHOAL (E2)

The fine shoal experiment lasted $2\text{ h } 29\text{ min}$ however the front of the shoal reached the downstream end of the flume in $1\text{ h } 25\text{ min}$. The front of the shoal already propagated about 20 cm while the flume was filled with water. The moment the experiment started some alternating bars formed, shortly thereafter they evolved into downstream propagating dunes over the full width of the flume. Then the shoal propagated as multiple consecutive dunes. Downstream of the shoal was almost no transport of the original bed material. The first profile was taken directly after the flow was imposed on the flume. The original end of the shoal was at 4 m, but since the first profile of the bed and water level was taken after the flow was imposed on the flume the shoal already travelled 1 meter downstream in the first profile. Profiles of each measurement are in Appendix C.

Three regions are analysed for the flow conditions, the bed level and the grain size distribution.

1. The shoal front
2. The region downstream of the shoal front
3. The region upstream of the shoal front

4.2.1 FLOW CONDITIONS

On top of the shoal the Bernoulli effect is visible as a small increase of the water level downstream of each dune which can be seen in the water level profiles in Appendix C. Downstream of the shoal front there are waves in the water surface and there is also slight

increase of the average water level in the region directly downstream of the shoal. The Froude number downstream of the shoal was around 0.5. Upstream of the shoal front the water level was, besides the small differences because of the Bernoulli effect, constant but the dunes in the bed made the water depth varied. Therefore the Froude number above the shoal varied between 0.5 and 0.75 with high values on top of the dunes.

The Froude number on top of the wooden structure was 0.65. So the flow was subcritical over the whole flume.

4.2.2 BED LEVEL

The shoal propagated as dunes to the downstream end of the flume. Figure 7 shows the position of the front of the shoal in time. The celerity was quite uniform over time until the shoal reached the downstream end. At that time did not propagate anymore, but the shoal material started to fill up this area that was eroded while filling the flume with water. The front of the shoal moved with a celerity of 4.1 m/h.

Downstream of the shoal front the original mixed bed was barely affected by the shoal, as can be seen in Figure 9. There is no significant erosion in this part. During the experiment also the original bed was barely mobile.

The dunes in the shoal are clearly visible in Figure 8, the different dunes moved with a different celerity, so faster dunes over took the slower ones. Once they caught up the two dunes moved on as one new dune. Also once a dune caught up with the shoal front, it got trapped there and moved on with the front at the same celerity as the shoal front. At the upstream end of the shoal a scour pit was formed. The scour here provided the sediment for the downstream propagation of the shoal, in the first half hour of the experiment it deepened quite fast, but after that the scour deepened with 1.3 cm/h and it did not widen much more. The dunes started in the scour pit. This is well visible in the profiles (Appendix C).

FIGURE 7 PROPAGATION OF THE SHOAL FRONT AND A LINEAR FIT APPLIED TO THE DATA. AFTER 1 H 25 MIN THE SHOAL FRONT REACHED THE DOWNSTREAM END OF THE FLUME AND WAS OUT OF THE REACH OF THE MEASURING INSTRUMENTS.

FIGURE 8 THE BED LEVEL DURING E2. THE PROPAGATING DUNES ARE WELL DEFINED. THE BED DOWNSTREAM OF THE SHOAL KEEPS THE SAME ELEVATION UNTIL THE SHOAL TRAVELS OVER IT. THE DEEPENING OF THE SCOUR PIT IS ALSO WELL VISIBLE.

FIGURE 9 THE CHANGE IN BED ELEVATION RELATIVE TO THE FIRST MEASURED BED PROFILE. AT SOME PLACES THE INITIAL ELEVATION WAS REACHED UPSTREAM OF A DUNE, THE CELERITY OF THE DUNES UPSTREAM OF THESE PLACES IS SIMILAR TO THE CELERITY OF THE ORIGINAL SHOAL FRONT. THE BLACK LINE INDICATES THE PLACE WHERE THE SHOAL FRONT WAS INSTALLED BEFORE THE EXPERIMENT STARTED.

4.2.3 GRAIN SIZE DISTRIBUTION

While the shoal propagated, the shoal material did not travel further than the front. The first data point downstream the shoal in Figure 10 and Figure 11 shows a gradual change in grain sizes because the grain size and the fractions are averaged over each bed photo. The photo of the bed at the shoal front has the shoal material on one side and the bed material on the other side. In Appendix C the bed elevations, the shoal fraction and the coarse bed fraction are plotted in one figure per time step, grain size distribution and the bed elevation at the shoal front travel with the same celerity.

Upstream of the shoal front the bed surface consisted only of the shoal fraction in the first half hour. At some points the original bed got exposed, resulting in a higher mean grain size and a lower fraction of shoal material. Most of the sediment from original bed that got exposed were from the coarse fraction and therefore it was not mobile. The dunes upstream of the places where the original bed got exposed had a celerity similar to the shoal front. The shoal travelling over the coarser bed had a fining effect on the bed surface upstream, but had almost no influence on the bed downstream (Figure 11).

In the reach downstream of the shoal there was initially an overrepresentation of the coarse fraction. This overrepresentation lasted until the bed was covered with the shoal material. The original bed was barely mobile so the grain size distribution did not change much. Resulting in only minor changes in grainsize distribution (Figure 10).

FIGURE 10 THE MEAN GRAIN SIZE PER TIME STEP. THE DOWNSTREAM REGION DID NOT CHANGE MUCH. AT THE PLACES WHERE THE ORIGINAL BED GOT EXPOSED THE MEAN GRAIN SIZE WAS COARSER THAN THE SHOAL BUT FINER THAN THE ORIGINAL BED.

FIGURE 11 THE SHOAL FRACTION PER TIME STEP. NO SHOAL MATERIAL TRAVELLED IN FRONT OF THE SHOAL. THE FIRST POINT DOWNSTREAM THE SHOAL IS MIXED BECAUSE THE PHOTO CONTAINED BOTH A PART OF THE SHOAL AND THE ORIGINAL MIXED BED.

4.2.4 SEDIMENT DISCHARGE

In this experiment the sediment discharge was measured but the obtained values are not representative of the sediment discharge for two reasons. First the sediment transport over the downstream reach was low and secondly the shoal first filled up the end of the flume and thus did not end up in the sediment trap.

4.3 COARSE SHOAL (E3)

The coarse shoal experiment lasted $7\text{ h } 11\text{ min}$, the experiment was stopped after the bed did not change rapidly anymore. The first profile was taken directly after the flow, determined in E1, was imposed on the flume. After 3 hours the original bed got exposed and because of the higher mobility started moving, this created a second shoal (Shoal 2). The material from the scour mixed with the material in the first shoal (Shoal 1), so this shoal got finer. Shortly after this, at $3\text{ h } 47\text{ min}$, a scour hole was created at the upstream end of the shoal due to an error in placing the boat of the camera cart.

In this experiment were two distinct phases, Phase 1 with only one shoal in the first 3 hours and Phase 2 where there were 2 shoal fronts. Phase 1 has the same three regions of interest as the fine shoal experiment, while in Phase 2 also the region between the two shoals is of interest.

1. The region downstream of the shoal front
2. The region upstream of the shoal front
3. The region between the two fronts (only Phase 2)
4. The shoal front
5. The second shoal front (only Phase 2)

4.3.1 FLOW CONDITIONS

During Phase 1 the flow over the bed was sub critical, the Froude number varied around 0.7 on the shoal and around 0.5 on the bed. While the bed downstream of the shoal eroded but the downstream water level was kept constant, so the flow velocity and Froude number decreased on this part over time.

In Phase 2, the Froude number on the original shoal decreased gradually from almost 0.7 to around 0.5, also downstream this shoal the Froude number decreased from 0.5 to 0.4. On the new shoal the Froude number stayed the same as on the original shoal in Phase 1.

The flow at the inlet on top of the wooden structure was in the trans critical zone, Froude numbers between 0.9 and 1.1, during the entire experiment. Downstream the structure the Froude number lowered into the subcritical regime, but this created some standing waves.

4.3.2 *BED LEVEL*

The coarse shoal has a different effect on the downstream original bed than the fine shoal. The reach downstream of the shoal has a lower mean grain size and is thus much more mobile than the shoal material, even though the flow velocity on the shoal is higher. This sudden change in transport capacity created a scour hole downstream of the shoal, Scour 1, and erosion over the whole downstream bed.

The material needed for the shoal to propagate downstream was provided by the whole upstream bed. This is visible in Figure 13, as the bed at 2 meter upstream of the shoal front is light orange indicating erosion. Also at the centre the bed eroded faster than at the walls. These two effects contributed to the exposure of the original bed underneath the shoal. First the coarse particles became visible and after that also the fine particles. The sudden higher mobility created a second scour (Scour 2) and Shoal 2. Also Shoal 1 got cut off of the supply of shoal material.

The region between the two fronts became smaller as the celerity of Shoal 1 decreased while the celerity of Shoal 2 stays relatively constant. Scour 2 provided the sediment for the propagation of Shoal 1. Scour 2 was less radical than the first scour and in time Shoal 2 ran over it decreasing the scour depth. The scour depth of Scour 1 kept increasing during the whole experiment.

Shoal 1 moved in two stages, first with only the shoal material, until the shoal material became scarce and the shoal slowed down. Once the Scour 2 was formed the sediment budget for the original shoal increased due to the scour of the original bed, but after the Shoal travelled over the scour the sediment budget rapidly decreased resulting a decreasing celerity (Figure 14). The total average celerity of Shoal 1 is 0.55 m/h . Shoal 2 propagated with a more constant celerity of 0.75 m/h .

The error with the measuring instrument at the upstream end of the flume induced the scour. Once induced the scour hole started to grow, providing the sediment for the propagation of the shoal. Directly downstream of the scour a sudden increase of the bed level is visible in Figure 12 (shortly before 4 hours into the experiment).

FIGURE 12 THE BED LEVEL IN THE COARSE SHOAL EXPERIMENT. ALL THE DIFFERENT PROCESSES ARE WELL VISIBLE. AT FIRST THE SHOAL PROPAGATED IN ONE FRONT WITH A DOWNSTREAM SCOUR. AFTER 3 HOURS THE SECOND SCOUR STARTED AND THE SECOND SHOAL WAS FORMED. THE UPSTREAM SCOUR INCREASED ONCE IT WAS INDUCED.

FIGURE 13 THE CHANGE IN BED LEVEL RELATIVE TO THE FIRST BED LEVEL PROFILE. THE OVERALL EROSION OF THE BED IS WELL VISIBLE, DARKER ORANGE MEANS MORE EROSION AT THAT POINT. THE BLACK LINE INDICATES THE POSITION WHERE THE SHOAL FRONT WAS INSTALLED.

FIGURE 14 THE POSITION AND THE PROPAGATION CELERITY OF THE ORIGINAL AND NEW SHOAL. THE CELERITY OF THE ORIGINAL SHOAL CHANGES IN TIME, BUT THE CELERITY OF THE NEW SHOAL IS FAIRLY CONSTANT.

4.3.3 GRAIN SIZE DISTRIBUTION

In Phase 1 the bed surface upstream of the shoal front consisted entirely of shoal material. Until after 2 hours coarse grains of the original bed became visible due to the erosion of the shoal. At the place where the original bed got exposed, first the coarse particles were visible and 1 hour thereafter also the fine ones. The moment the fine grains came to the surface that part of the bed was more mobile and the scour started. This is clearly visible in the profiles (Appendix D). As result of this process the original shoal mixed with bed material, reducing the mean grain size but still more than 50% of the material in the mixed shoal was shoal material. After 5 h and 30 min there were again some coarse grains visible at the same place as the scour started the first time but this time sediment from Scour 3 was transported over this place before the fine grains got exposed.

There was no shoal material moving further than the front for both Shoal 1 and 2 in both phases.

In the reach downstream of the shoal front there was initially an overrepresentation of the coarse fraction in the first three profiles, this overrepresentation travelled downstream within the first hour of the experiment. After that the grain size distribution in the original bed was around 50% fine and 50% coarse until the end of the experiment. This indicates a higher mobility of the downstream reach.

4.3.4 SEDIMENT DISCHARGE

Measuring of the sediment discharge started 17 min after the first profile was taken. Because the connection to the computer did not work the mass in the box was measured regularly. Using formula 2, 3 and 4 the sediment discharge was calculated. The sediment discharge gradually decreases in time (Appendix E). No shoal material reached the sand trap. Since no sediment was coming from the shoal there was less bed material left to move downstream decreasing the sediment discharge. Also the water depth increased, due to the decreasing bed level while the water level stayed constant, therefore the flow velocity decreased in time at the downstream and thus the transport capacity of the flow.

FIGURE 15 THE MEAN GRAIN SIZE IN DURING E3. THE FIRST HALF HOUR THE OVERREPRESENTATION OF THE COARSE BED FRACTION TRAVELS OUT OF THE DOMAIN. THE MOMENT THE NEW SHOAL WAS FORMED THE MEAN GRAIN SIZE OF THE BED BETWEEN THE TWO SHOAL FRONTS DECREASES.

FIGURE 16 THE SHOAL FRACTION DURING E3. NO SHOAL MATERIAL WAS MOVING IN FRONT OF THE SHOAL FRONTS. THE SCOUR HOLE DOWNSTREAM OF THE NEW SHOAL CONSISTED MAINLY OF THE BED MATERIAL FROM THE ORIGINAL BED. DOWNSTREAM OF THE SCOUR THE FRACTIONS MIXED WHERE MOSTLY THE SHOAL FRACTION WAS PRESENT.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 THE EXPERIMENT

5.1.1 USE OF TWO DIFFERENT FLUMES

The fine shoal experiment was done in a different flume than the normal flow experiment and the coarse shoal experiment. While the properties of both flumes are equal, the wooden structure was different in both flumes. In the flume of the fine shoal experiment the top of the structure was covered with coarse grains while the structure in the other flume was covered with coarse sand. This difference in roughness implied two different inflow conditions, so the incoming flow in both the shoal experiments was not equal. This needs to be taken into account in the interpretation of the results. The trans critical flow on the structure in the coarse shoal experiment was not present in the normal flow experiment because the water level above the structure was higher during the normal flow than during the coarse shoal experiment.

5.1.2 CONCAVITY OF THE BED

The grains in the centre of the flume were more mobile than the grains that were situated near the walls of the flume. Higher friction at the walls reduced the flow velocity, at lower flow velocities the shear stress at the bed surface is lower and thus the capacity to entrain sediment. Also secondary circulations in the flume decreased the transport capacity at the walls. Due to these effects the cross section of the bed was concave.

In the fine shoal experiment this effect was more visible in the shoal than in the original bed. At the places in the shoal where the original bed was visible the sediment at the walls was still almost only the fine shoal material. The original bed was first visible in the centre of the flume.

In the coarse shoal experiment the shoal travelled downstream first through the middle of the flume filling up the concave. The concave was present in both the shoal as the original bed. The concavity of the shoal probably promoted the exposure of the original bed while there was erosion in the middle of the flume. The original bed below that point in the shoal was less affected by the concavity because it was covered with shoal material quickly after the experiment started. The combination of erosion and concavity exposed the original bed after which the scour of the bed started.

5.1.3 INFLUENCE OF THE ERROR WITH THE BOAT

In the profiles (Figure 12 and Figure 13) it is well visible that after the accident with the boat for the camera happened the upstream scour hole was formed. After the formation it continued to grow rapidly, while before there was a small start of a scour hole at that point but that hole did not grow significantly.

At 5 h 31 min again some of the original bed got exposed at almost the same place as the first exposure of the original bed, but this time it was covered again with shoal material in the next measurement. Probably further exposure was prevented by the extra sediment coming from the scour.

5.1.4 NO SEDIMENT FEED

The upstream part of the bed, the shoal, was completely constructed out of the shoal material. So there was no sediment feed but the shoal was long enough to provide sediment for the propagation of the shoal front. The effect of the shoal on the downstream bed is measured but what happens to the bed when a shoal has propagated over the bed is not measured. The final effect of a coarse or fine shoal travelling over a mixed bed is not measured. But at places where the original bed got exposed the grain size distribution was finer or coarser in the fine shoal and coarse shoal experiment respectively. In the experiments done by Sklar et al. (2009) the finer sediment cause an over-all fining of a coarse bed, so it can be expected that the finer shoal decreases the mean grain size for a longer time after it would have travelled over the entire bed.

A coarse augmentation will have a coarsening effect or it will armour the bed leading to no sediment transport.

5.2 IMPLICATIONS FOR SEDIMENT AUGMENTATIONS IN RIVERS

The experiments are not scaled to a specific river, but they are done to study the general influences of sediment augmentations. The processes observed in the experiments will hold when augmenting finer or coarser sediment than the sediment in the bed. However it is not sure to what extent the bed forms and deformations will occur.

The objective of an augmentation will determine whether or not the augmentation is successful and depending on that objective of a sediment augmentation a coarser or finer augmentation material should be used. The objective can be in a change in grain size distribution or a change in bed level or a combination of those two.

- Improving the grain size distribution: fining or coarsening
- Compensate for erosion

For improving the grain size distribution the fine and the coarse shoal will have the required effect for fining and coarsening respectively. But for how long the effect will last is not sure. By coarsening the bed it will be less mobile and the coarsening can last. By fining the bed the bed becomes more mobile. If the transport capacity of the flow is high enough to transport the augmented sediment, there is a chance that the augmentation will travel out of the projected reach for the improvement. Due to the hiding effects also coarser grains can become mobile and leave the reach eventually coarsening the bed.

A coarse augmentation is likely to affect the downstream bed: this part will erode more. Increasing the bed level by adding coarse sediment will migrate the erosion downstream. Also while a coarse augmentation propagates downstream a river, the transport capacity of the river decreases. There will be a point where the grains are not mobile anymore and fill a part of the river with an armoured bed, reducing the sediment budget downstream causing more erosion at that point. Generally a coarser bed is less mobile, so at the place of the coarse augmentation that part of the bed will be less vulnerable for further degradation.

Compensating for erosion with a fine augmentation will have a better effect, this increases the bed level and does not affect the downstream bed. The fine shoal travelled quite fast downstream so the net effect of one augmentation is small. Doing more augmentations to keep the bed level the same is also more expensive. If the material of a fine augmentation propagates far enough downstream it will reach a point where the grains will be coarse relative to the original bed material and it might evolve into a coarse shoal. If the dunes from the experiment also form in a fine augmentation in a river they can be harmful to navigation. When the dunes decrease the local water depth too much, ships can get damaged or will not be able to navigate further upstream.

To restore rivers ecologically sediment augmentations are a good measure. When large amounts of sediments are augmented there is a chance that the new material will cover the whole bed. This can be harmful for the ecology if it is not well understood or researched beforehand. In all augmentation projects this should be held in consideration.

By choosing the grain size for augmentations, there is a trade-off between degradation downstream versus the long term effect of the augmentation in the grain size distribution. In each project the objective and the unwanted effects have to be clear beforehand, so the best suitable augmentation sediment can be chosen.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

6.1 RECOMMENDATIONS

If future experiments on shoal propagation will be done the experiments could be improved by adjusting the experimental setup. Instead of using a full depth shoal a sediment feed can be used with on a mixed bed. After a set period the feed with shoal material can switch to a feed with the normal sediment discharge. In that way the effects of an augmentation on both the reach downstream of the augmentation as the reach over which it propagated can be studied.

To reduce the effect of the wall on the sediment discharge a wider flume can be used.

In the experiments vertical mixing was not measured, this is a feature that can be easily measured after the experiment ended. The interaction between the shoal material and the original bed material and especially the infiltration of the fine shoal material into the original bed can give more insight for restoration projects that aim to improve the riverbed for spawning.

6.2 CONCLUSIONS

Three experiments were done to find the influence of both a fine and a coarse augmentation on a mixed bed done by a shoal in. The behaviour and the effects of both shoals are significantly different. In the fine shoal experiment the original bed was barely mobile and the downstream reach did not erode. The shoal increased the bed level locally, however it propagated as a series of dunes so the bed was less smooth at these places.

The mobility of the mixed bed downstream of the coarse shoal increased. Due to this higher mobility a scour pit was formed directly downstream the shoal front and further downstream the bed eroded significantly. The shoal propagated with one shoal front. On both the shoal as de reach downstream of the shoal front no bed forms were present.

The fine shoal moved with a celerity 7 times as fast as the coarse shoal. In both cases there was no shoal material that propagated further downstream than the shoal front.

These findings need to be taken into account when the grain size distributions are chosen for sediment augmentations.

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APPENDICES

A. MEASURING INSTRUMENTS

Below the different measuring instruments are depicted.

FIGURE A. 1 CARRIAGE TO MEASURE THE WATER LEVEL AND BED LEVEL; A: WATER LEVEL LASER, B: BED LEVEL LASER, WHEN MEASURING THIS LASER IS BELOW THE WATER LEVEL

FIGURE A. 2 CARRIAGE TO TAKE THE PICTURES OF THE BED, THE GLASS BOAT CAN BE LOWERED TO THE WATER SURFACE.

FIGURE A. 3 FLOW METER

FIGURE A. 5 SEDIMENT TRAP AT THE DOWNSTREAM END OF THE FLUME; A: SEDIMENT PUMP, B: WEIR TO REGULATE THE DOWNSTREAM WATER LEVEL

FIGURE A. 4 BOX TO COLLECT THE SEDIMENT ON THE SCALE; A: COLLECTOR BOX, B: SCALE DISPLAY

B. DISTRIBUTION OF FRACTIONS BEFORE AND AFTER THE NORMAL FLOW EXPERIMENT (E1)

The graphs show the areal and volumetric fractions of the coarse and fine bed fractions during the normal flow experiment. The first bed was before the flow was started, the method that was used to flatten the bed tends to over represent the coarse grains in the bed surface.

C. PROFILES OF THE BED AND WATER LEVEL AND THE GRAIN SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF THE BED SURFACE IN THE FINE SHOAL EXPERIMENT (E2)

Each figure shows first the bed level and the water level at the different times that the profiles were measured. The bed level is plotted against the initial bed level. Secondly the propagation of the shoal fraction is plotted, also relative to the initial distribution. The propagating dunes are clearly visible.

D. PROFILES OF THE BED AND WATER LEVEL AND THE GRAIN SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF THE BED SURFACE IN THE COARSE SHOAL EXPERIMENT (E3)

Each figure shows first the bed level and the water level at the different times that the profiles were measured. The bed level is plotted against the initial bed level. Secondly the propagation of the shoal fraction is plotted, also relative to the initial distribution. In the last measurements standing waves cause by inflow effects are visible in the plots. The high flow made it hard to make perfect water level profiles.

E. SEDIMENT DISCHARGE (E3)

The sediment discharge in the coarse shoal experiment. The sediment discharge decreased over time, both visible in the net discharge [kg] where the graph flattens as in the sediment discharge per unit width where there is a trend visible that goes to zero.

